

Falcon

Foreseeing the next generation of Aircraft

D5.2. Report on algorithm design, code
porting and optimization

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List of acronyms	
CAS	Computer Algebra System
CSE	Common Subexpression Elimination
CPU	CPU (Central Processing Unit
CUDA	Compute Unified Device Architect
DSL	Domain Specific Language
EC	European Commission
FP	Floating Point
FSI	Fluid-structure interaction
GPU	Graphics Processing Unit
LB	Lattice Boltzmann
LBM	Lattice Boltzmann Method
LES	Large Eddy Simulation
HRRLBM	Hybrid Homogenized Regularized Recursive Lattice Boltzmann
MPI	Message Passing Interface
RRLBM	Regularized Recursive Lattice Boltzmann
SIMD	Single Instruction, Multiple Data
WM	Wall Model
WP	Work Package

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2. Algorithm design, code porting, and optimization

The objective of Task 5.2 is the efficient implementation of algorithms developed in WP2, focusing on both single-node performance and scalability on modern GPU-accelerated clusters.

During the first reporting period, each partner focuses on developing particular features within their tool to allow computation of the three industrial test cases defined in the FALCON project proposal. Hence, the optimizations described below are related to each tool separately.

3. OpenLB (KIT)

All KIT-developed methods of WP2 and WP4 are realized in the context of the open source (GPL2) C++ framework OpenLB, a major open-source project for the implementation of LBM-based multi-physics simulations. Being in active development since 2007, it not only provides an extensive library of LB models covering a large variety of multi-physics applications but supports transparent execution of optimized LB models on heterogeneous high performance computers. For FALCON and the present Deliverable 5.2, a new automatic code generation and optimization pipeline was implemented¹²; enabling the transparent optimization of the new collision operators and non-local boundary condition implementations required for wall-modeled FSI. This code generation pipeline was applied to the models developed in WP2 and evaluated both in isolated roofline studies as well as for parallel scalability on different supercomputers.

3.1. Platform-transparent Implementation

At its core, OpenLB provides a framework for operating efficiently and in parallel on data associated with discrete spatial locations in a regular lattice³. In this context, data views are provided on the cell-level and operators are implemented as C++ templates accepting the *concept of a cell*. This abstraction enables instantiation of abstract model implementations for concrete data structures that are optimized for the specific target platform. For example, the cells used for vectorized CPU resp. CUDA-based GPU execution can be and are completely separate, their only connection is the common interface exposed to the model code⁴. This basic principle is illustrated by Figure 1 and put into the general framework context by Figure 2.

Figure 1: Generic model structure in OpenLB and interface to CSE-optimized operators including adjoints (cf. WP4). Figure taken from [3].

¹ [1] Ito et al. Generation of efficient adjoint lattice Boltzmann methods using automatic differentiation. 2026. In preparation.

² [2] Kummerländer et al. Large-Scale Simulations of Turbulent Flows using Lattice Boltzmann Methods on Heterogeneous High Performance Computers. In: High Performance Computing in Science and Engineering '25 (accepted). Springer. Preprint DOI: [10.48550/arXiv.2506.21804](https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2506.21804)

³ [3] Kummerländer et al. OpenLB: An Efficient and Flexible Lattice Boltzmann Method Framework on Heterogeneous High Performance Computers. 2025. In preparation.

⁴ [4] Kummerländer et al. Optimization of single node load balancing for lattice Boltzmann method on heterogeneous high performance computers. 2025. In: Journal of Parallel and Distributed Computing. DOI: [10.1016/j.jpdc.2025.105169](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpdc.2025.105169)

The solid blue boxes highlight parts of OpenLB applications that users commonly modify and extend while solid yellow boxes represent the core classes of the framework. Dashed yellow boxes represent the specific classes that interface between abstraction layers. Solid green boxes highlight the lowest-level platform-specific data storage and view classes.

Figure 2: Simplified overview of OpenLB's software architecture. Figure taken from [3].

Notably, the concepts that isolate the user-level model code (blue boxes in Figure 2) from the platform-specific data structures are declared as C++20 concepts.

3.2. Automatic Code Optimization

The HRRRLBM collision model developed in WP2 was expressed in terms of OpenLB's *dynamics* tuple DSL, enabling straight forward combination with other models such as LES in addition to platform-transparent executability across CPUs and GPUs. The following listing describes the HRRRLBM-LES scheme used for WP2⁵.

⁵ [5] Kummerländer et al. Efficient Wall-Modelled Large Eddy Simulation of Rotors using Homogenized Lattice Boltzmann Methods. 2025. Under review. Preprint DOI: [10.48550/arXiv.2510.13726](https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2510.13726)

```
using HRRRLBM = dynamics::Tuple<
    T, descriptors::D3Q19<>, // Value type and lattice stencil
    typename momenta::Tuple< // Macroscopic moment system
        momenta::BulkDensity,
        momenta::MovingPorousMomentumCombination<momenta::BulkMomentum>, // HLBM porosity term
        momenta::BulkStress,
        momenta::DefineToNEq
    >,
    equilibria::ThirdOrder, // Equilibrium distribution
    collision::ParameterFromCell< // Modified collision operator
        collision::LES::SMAGORINSKY, // Using local Smagorinsky constant
        collision::SmagorinskyEffectiveOmega<collision::ThirdOrderRLB>>
>;
```

Due to the abstract implementation of all LB models against the concept of a cell they are not only amenable to platform-transparent execution but also automatic code optimization using CSE. This optimization considers the arithmetic operations that constitute any model (in the present LBM case usually collision steps and additional non-local operators) on the symbolic level in a CAS. In this context common subexpressions, i.e. parts of the arithmetic tree that occur more than once, are identified and extracted into temporary variables for re-use. This can significantly reduce the total number of arithmetic operations performed for the model without changing the results (beyond cut-off and rounding errors that are inherent in FP arithmetic).

Figure 3: Interface of simulation case and CSE optimization pipeline. Taken from [3].

For the HRRRLBM model used in the wall-modeled FSI regions, OpenLB reports a per-collision memory bandwidth of 204 bytes and a FP complexity of 1618 FLOPs (cf. 4697 FLOPs in the

Roofline analysis on the theoretical peak performance of an NVIDIA A100 GPU (left) resp. H100 GPU (right). CSE optimization is critical for reducing the arithmetic intensity of both the bulk and wall-modeled collision steps, rendering them bandwidth-limited in the ideal case. Memory and compute roofs given by theoretical maximums provided in the data sheets by NVIDIA.

Figure 4: Roofline analysis of local cell models for NVIDIA GPUs Taken from [2,5].

unoptimized case, a ~ 2.9 fold reduction). Similarly, the bulk non-FSI RRLBM model has a bandwidth of 152 bytes per cell and requires 1189 FLOPs per collision after a 3.8-fold CSE optimization. A theoretical roofline analysis for the involved dynamics utilizing OpenLB’s introspection data is shown in Figure 4 for both NVIDIA A100 and H100 GPUs. Both roofline plots clearly show that CSE is critical for moving the bulk collision steps and as such the combined problem from being compute-limited into the bandwidth-restricted region (visible by their move from the upper-right to the lower-left on the roofline plot). The performance impact of this optimization on an A100 GPU is summarized in Table 1.

Table 1: Arithmetic and bandwidth intensity as well as isolated speedup on A100 GPU. Figure taken from [5].

Dynamics	Bandwidth [bytes]	Operations [FLOPs]			Performance [MLUPs]		
		No-CSE	CSE	Reduction	No-CSE	CSE	Speedup
RRLBM	152	4512	1189	2.90	2885	6411	2.22
HHRRLBM	204	4697	1618	3.79	2373	4252	1.79

3.3. Scalability

The main targets for code optimization are the HoreKa supercomputer of NHR@KIT, the Karolina supercomputer at IT4I (EuroHPC) and the Leonardo supercomputer at CINCECA (EuroHPC). While all those systems are accelerated by NVIDIA GPUs that are fully supported by OpenLB, computations for surrogate training (WP4) are targeted to be performed on the LUMI supercomputer (EuroHPC) which is accelerated by AMD GPUs. While they are currently unsupported, the framework architecture is designed to allow adaptation.

Software optimizations of OpenLB targeted at the local KIT cluster HoreKa translate directly to both Leonardo and Karolina due to the very similar hardware structure (NVIDIA GPUs of the same generation, Infiniband interconnect). On a single Karolina node (8x NVIDIA A100 40GB), initial benchmarks yielded a throughput of 47 Billion Cell Updates per Second (GLUPs) for a problem size of one billion cells. This enabled the direct use for development and evaluation of the new methods in WP2 and WP4. On a single Leonardo node (4x NVIDIA A100 64GB), initial benchmarks yielded a throughput of 22 Billion Cell Updates per Second (GLUPs) for a problem size of 125 million cells. This is in line with performance results on HoreKa Green, also using 4x A100 per node.

Since the start of the reporting period, HoreKa gained a new partition with more capable NVIDIA H100 GPUs. To validate that the models built inside OpenLB for WPs 2 and 4 can take advantage of this newer hardware, strong and weak scaling benchmarks were performed both for a standard lid driven cavity case, the full wall-modeled LES setup with turbulent inlet condition of WP2, as well as a WM-FSI validation case for the flow around a rotor.

Size	HoreKa Blue		HoreKa Green		HoreKa Teal	
	[32→128]	[64→128]	[32→128]	[64→128]	[4→16]	[8→16]
575 ³	0.66	0.78	0.45	0.72	0.48	0.80
725 ³	0.83	0.96	0.53	0.72	0.54	0.83
913 ³	0.76	0.94	0.46	0.64	0.56	0.83
1150 ³	0.75	0.89	0.57	0.71	0.62	0.86
1449 ³	0.76	0.86	0.60	0.71	0.67	0.91
1826 ³	0.79	0.89	0.67	0.77	—	—
2200 ³	0.84	0.91	—	0.80	—	—
2300 ³	—	—	—	0.81	—	—

Figure 5: Left: Combined weak- and strong-scaling analysis of OpenLB on HoreKa Teal for problem sizes between 190 million and 3 billion cells. Right: Strong-scaling values for all partitions of HoreKa. Both taken from [2].

Figure 5 shows a combined weak- and strong-scaling analysis of OpenLB on HoreKa Teal for problem sizes between 190 million and 3 billion cells. Black lines mark the weak scaling efficiencies while the colored lines mark the strong-scaling behavior for their respective problem size. The table summarizes strong-scaling values for all partitions of HoreKa.

Figure 6: Combined weak- and strong-scaling analysis for a full WM-LES-HHRLBM numerical wind channel case, including a turbulent inlet condition. Figure taken from [2].

This scalability study was also performed for a full WM-LES-HHRLBM numerical wind channel case, including a turbulent inlet condition. Figure 6 shows weak- and strong efficiencies for problem sizes between 0.5 and 8 billion cells utilizing between 4 and 32 NVIDIA H100 GPUs.

The weak scaling study utilizes a wind farm setup placing one turbine per A100 GPU using between 1 and 64 nodes of Karolina's accelerated partition. The setup is based directly on the validated rotor case, changing only the number of turbines in a NxM grid but still performing the full wall-modeled FSI simulation with computation of the integral thrust values at every timestep.

Figure 7: Weak scaling analysis of wind farm on Karolina. Figure taken from [5].

Based on the validated wall-modeled rotor case we performed simulations of up to 512 rotors resolved by up to 54 billion cells on 512 NVIDIA 100 GPUs of the Karolina supercomputer. This demonstrates the scalability of multi-GPU support for complex cases combining moving wall-modeled geometries. Two different resolutions $N = \{20,30\}$ (measured over the tip width of the rotor airfoil) were tested, both providing high quality results w.r.t. integral reference quantities [5]. The tested problem sizes range between $30e6$ and $54e9$ cells with a peak throughput of $562e9$ cell updates per second for this complex wall-modeled application case.

For the larger $N = 30$ case near ideal weak scaling efficiency above 92% is observed up to 64 GPUs after which the efficiency reduces to 69 % for the 54 billion cell case on 512 GPUs. This reduction also persists if all global reductions are disabled, hinting at inter-node communication latency restrictions caused e.g. by non-contiguous allocation of higher node counts.

4. ESPRESO (VSB-TUO)

4.1. Optimization of the ESPRESO library

The three parts of the ESPRESO library that were optimized within the FALCON project are the contact search algorithm, physical assembler of corotation formulation, and assembling of the conjugate projector. The optimizations are described in more detail in the following subsections. The presented results were measured on Karolina, the main development cluster of the FALCON project.

4.2. Contact search

The efficient contact search algorithm is fundamental for the computation of the TC2 and TC3 examples where the contact between bodies emerges. In addition, the contact search is also part of the initialization of FSI simulations, where, at the beginning of the simulation, the contact interface must be found.

The contact search algorithm can be divided into global and local search. During the global search, MPI processes must exchange surface elements that are in potential contact with the surface elements of other processes. In ESPRESO, we implemented it using bounding boxes. They are simple to compute,

Figure 8: Tube in Tube: the model used for testing the contact search algorithm.

whereas they should sufficiently bound elements on a given process as the mesh is decomposed by METIS to relatively well-shaped domains. Bounding boxes can be stored using 6 floats only (minimal and maximal coordinates). Then, during the global search, each process sends its bounding box to the others by a single MPI_Allgather routine. Despite the gathering being a global operation, as only 6 floats per process are exchanged, it is relatively fast. Then, all processes compute the intersection with other processes and send their surface elements to them. After this nearest-neighbour operation, local search is applied to each process separately (without further communication). The local search is implemented using interval trees and the Sutherland–Hodgman polygon clipping algorithm. First, each surface element is represented with a box enlarged according to a gap defined by a user to consider that the spatially close elements are in contact. These boxes are checked for intersection with the interval tree, reducing the complexity from $O(n^2)$ to $O(n \log n)$. If the boxes intersect, the exact contact is computed with the Sutherland–Hodgman algorithm.

The measurement was tested on the tube in a tube example depicted in Figure 8. The efficiency of the contact search (including all the steps) is depicted in Figure 9. The model is composed of 3 million

tetrahedra. The contact search on 2 MPI processes takes 4.18s. The same example on 128 MPI processes takes 0.3 s.

Figure 9: The strong scalability of the contact search algorithm in ESPRESO.

4.3. Physical assembler

The physical assembler must process each element of the input geometry. To speed up the assembly process, intrinsic instructions are used to utilize SIMD registers in the CPU. Using these registers, the CPU can perform requested instructions with more values at once (e.g., multiply 4 doubles in the case of the AVX2 instruction set). In the ESPRESO library, we implemented common cross-elements approach for the vectorization (using SIMD instructions⁶). In such an approach, more elements are processed at once, which works in conjunction with the idea of SIMD instructions of processing more values simultaneously. The cross-element approach is widely used and typically achieves close to optimal speedup for compute-bound assemblers.

However, not all instructions can be easily vectorized. It is also the case with the newly implemented corotation formulation. It contains operations with large matrices and the computation of eigenvalues of assembled matrices. These factors degrade performance. The speedup of cross-element vectorization for corotation formulation can be seen in Figure 10. We can see that a speedup of about 1.5 was achieved with the AVX2 instruction set (blue line). With AVX2 instructions, a speedup of about 4 was expected. One of the reasons for the limited speedup was inefficient work with large matrices. By rearranging operations in the assembler and removing computation with zeros in the computed matrices, we achieved significant improvements (red line), especially for large elements (HEXA20, TETRA10, PRISMA15, PYRAMID13), for that it is hard to keep all the memory in CPU caches. Additional improvement was achieved by replacing the computation of eigenvalues and eigenvectors with the general LAPACK library, with manual implementation of the Smith algorithm for computation of eigenvalues for symmetric 3x3 matrices. Despite LAPACK being a heavily used and optimized library, it does not support simultaneous computation with several matrices, and it targets large matrices. With the Smith algorithm, we achieved a speedup of up to 5 (green line). Speedup is more significant for small elements where the computation of eigenvalues represents a significant portion of time.

⁶ [6] K. Kadlubiak, O. Meca, L. Říha, T. Brzobohatý. An approach for dynamically adaptable SIMD vectorization of FEM kernels, *Computer Physics Communications*, Volume 304, 2024, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cpc.2024.109319>.

Figure 10: Vectorization of the corotation assembler in ESPRESO.

4.4. Conjugate projector

A conjugate projector was implemented in the FETI solver to ensure convergence of transient problems. In general, projectors represent a bottleneck for FETI solvers as the complexity of the computation increases with the number of subdomains. To make the projector smaller, we also implement and optimize the conjugate projector for Hybrid FETI method⁷. This method introduces two-level decomposition, where the subdomains are grouped into clusters. Then, instead of computing the projector from subdomains, the projector is computed from clusters that efficiently reduce its size.

The conjugate projector is computed as $I - U(U^T F U)^{-1} U^T F$, where $U = BR$, B is gluing matrix, R is matrix with kernels of subdomain matrices, and F is the dual operator^{8,9}. For its evaluation, several strategies can be employed. In our approach, we use computation with explicit inversion¹⁰. In this approach, $(U^T F U)^{-1}$ is assembled and factorized on all processes. Then, each process computes a stripe related to subdomains/clusters held by a given process. Computing the explicit inversion enables a parallel application of the projector, which improves scalability.

⁷ [7] Brzobohatý, T., Jarošová, M., Kozubek, T., Mensík, M., Markopoulos, A., 2012. Hybrid Total FETI method. doi.org/10.4203/ccp.101.2.

⁸ [8] Ríha, L., Merta, M., Vavrik, R., Brzobohatý, T., Markopoulos, A., Meca, O., Vysocky, O., Kozubek, T., Vondrak, V., 2018. A massively parallel and memory-efficient FEM toolbox with a hybrid total FETI solver with accelerator support. The International Journal of High-Performance Computing Applications 33, 109434201879845. doi.org/10.1177/1094342018798452.

⁹ [9] Farhat, C., Chen, P.S., Mandel, J., 1995. A scalable lagrange multiplier based domain decomposition method for time-dependent problems. International Journal for Numerical Methods in Engineering 38, 3831–3853. doi.org/10.1002/nme.1620382207.

¹⁰ Ríha, L., Brzobohatý, T., Markopoulos, A., Meca, O., Kozubek, T., 2016. Massively Parallel Hybrid Total FETI (HTFETI) Solver, in: Proceedings of the Platform for Advanced Scientific Computing Conference, Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA. doi.org/10.1145/2929908.2929909

Besides the parallel computation of the inversion, it is also possible to parallelize the building of $U^T F U$. The parallelization is crucial, especially in the case of the conjugate projector with the F operator, since the number of columns in U is proportional to the number of subdomains or clusters.

Parallelization leverages the sparsity pattern of U , enabling the construction of $U^T F U$ in stripes per process with a nearest-neighbor communication pattern. The pattern of input matrices can be seen in Figure 11 with a problem decomposed into four subdomains (D1-D4) and glued by six Lagrange multipliers (A-F). Assuming each domain has a single kernel, the matrix U would have six rows and four columns. As the kernel of D1 has an intersection only with multipliers A and B, there will be non-zero values only in the first two rows of the first column in U (denoted by black squares). Due to the block structure of the operator F , only subdomains D1 and D2 contribute to the first column of $F U$. Hence, in the first column, $F U$ has non-zero values only in the first four rows, as subdomains D1 and D2 have only multipliers A-D. This propagation of non-zero values with the operator F to the neighbouring subdomains is denoted in the Figure 11 by the grey squares in the matrix $F U$. Due to this propagation, the final matrix has non-zero values in all positions $[U^T F U]_{ij}$ such that i -th and j -th kernels are of the subdomains connected with Lagrange multipliers through at most one another subdomain. E.g., the row related to the kernel of subdomain D2 will be fully filled, and the row related to the subdomain D1 will contain a zero value at the last column that is related to the kernel of subdomain D4.

Figure 11: Pattern in the conjugate projector.

Based on the observation above, one can use the following algorithm to assemble the projector:

1. assemble local contribution to U
2. exchange local contribution with neighbouring subdomains
3. assemble local contribution to $F U$
4. exchange local contribution with neighbouring subdomains
5. assemble local contribution to $U^T F U$
6. gather and factorize $U^T F U$
7. compute local stripe of $(U^T F U)^{-1}$

From a scalability perspective, steps 1, 3, 5, and 7 are embarrassingly parallel as they operate on the local part of the matrix. Steps 2 and 4 should remain constant, as the nearest-neighbour communication pattern is used. Step 6 contains factorization of a global object with the size proportional to the number of subdomains. It represents a bottleneck in FETI-based methods. Hence, to preserve scalability, the projector must be kept in a reasonable size, i.e., one must limit the number of subdomains or reduce the projector size by grouping the subdomains into clusters.

Omitting scalability issues, from a performance perspective, step 3 represents the most time-consuming part of the algorithm, especially for large subdomains. Although step 3 is local, the number of columns in U is proportional to the number of subdomains on a given process and their neighbours.

Let's have a uniform cubic decomposition. Then, the number of local columns in U for a single subdomain i is $d \times 3^3$, where d is the number of kernels of each subdomain. For $4 \times 4 \times 4$ subdomains in a cluster, it is $d \times 6^3$, i.e., several hundred. That is comparable to the number of iterations in the solution phase for which the dual operator is called. Hence, it is desirable to reduce the number of columns as much as possible. Reminding the example in Figure 4, the subdomain operator F has an effect (put non-zero values) only on columns related to kernels of neighboring subdomains. Hence, a simple filtering can be applied, reducing the application of F only to columns that contain non-zero values for a given subdomain. This filtering reduces the number of columns for each subdomain to $d \times 3^3$. Despite its simplicity, the filtering is fundamental from the performance perspective, as shown by the measurement in the Figure 12 and Figure 13.

Figure 12: Weak scalability of conjugate projector for FETI.

Figure 13: Weak scalability of conjugate projector for Hybrid FETI.

Figure 12 and Figure 13 present weak scalability for different numbers of subdomains per MPI process (cluster) and different numbers of unknowns per MPI process (cluster). The weak scalability of the conjugate projector for FETI demonstrates the limits and computational demands is the projector is assembled from subdomains. The weak scalability of the conjugate projector for Hybrid FETI demonstrates that two-level decomposition effectively surpasses these limits. The Hybrid FETI scalability figures also highlight the necessity of filtering in the application of the dual operator that reduces the maximum number of columns from U solved by the dual operator F .

Besides the overall time denoted by the solid lines, the figure also shows the increasing time of the sparse direct solver to factorize the matrix $U^T F U$ and compute its inversion, represented by dashes and dotted lines, respectively. We can observe a significant increase in factorization time and computation of inversion as the number of subdomains per cluster increases. Even though the inversion is computed by all processes in parallel, the direct solver must solve 6 right-hand sides per subdomain. For 80 and 320 subdomains per cluster, it is more time-consuming than the factorization. The size of the matrix $U^T F U$ is independent of the subdomain size; it is fully determined by the number of subdomains and their connectivity. Hence, factorization and inversion take the same amount of time regardless of the number of unknowns per cluster. Thus, it is possible to determine the minimal time needed to assemble the conjugate projector for a given decomposition with a given sparse direct solver.

To overcome the issues with a large projector, it is possible to group the subdomains into clusters and use Hybrid FETI, as shown in the bottom figures. Compared to FETI, the size of the projector in Hybrid FETI is proportional to the number of clusters. Hence, the factorization time and computation of the inversion are insignificant, around 0.02 and 0.001 seconds, respectively. Both are also independent of the number of subdomains per cluster. It allows setting the number of subdomains to be optimal from the dual operator point of view, i.e., minimizing the overall time of the FETI solver. In the case of the conjugate projector for Hybrid FETI, a significant part of the assembly process involves applying the dual operator to the matrix U , denoted by dotted lines, especially for clusters with many unknowns. Hence, this operation should be optimized. As can be observed, the positive effect of the filtering increases with the number of compute nodes used. It is caused by an increasing number of neighbouring clusters that are filtered out. For the largest clusters and 256 MPI processes, the filtering speeds up the application of the dual operator 3.4 times.

The time for all versions of the application of the dual operator to the matrix U increases with the number of MPI processes. For up to 64 processes, the time increases relatively quickly. Then, time increases more slowly. It is caused by an increasing number of neighbouring clusters. Hence, increasing the number of dual vectors. For 64 clusters, the uniformly decomposed cube contains clusters with the maximal number of neighbouring clusters (26 neighbouring clusters). Application of the dual operator for these clusters is the slowest (as the dual operator is applied to many dual vectors). Increasing the number of clusters above 64 does not increase the maximum number of neighbouring clusters, resulting in only a slight increase in overall computational time, primarily due to the factorization time.

5. LaBS (CS)

5.1. LaBS performance analysis

In the context of the Falcon project, preliminary performance tests were conducted on the LaBS solver, the LBM-based software solution developed by CS. All tests were performed on the Karolina clusters. Two separate studies were carried out: the first investigated the GPU version of LaBS, and the second examined the scalability of the CPU version.

All tests used TC1 with seven refinement levels. By decreasing the minimum mesh size, several test cases with varying numbers of fluid nodes were generated. For example, the smallest test case contains approximately 20 million fluid nodes.

5.2. GPU preliminary tests

The first GPU-enabled version of LaBS was successfully executed and its performance compared to the CPU version using several variants of the same test case. By decreasing the minimum mesh size (dx_{\min} in meters), three cases were obtained with approximately 20 million, 43 million, and 78 million fluid nodes. The relation between dx_{\min} and the number of fluid nodes is shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Relation between dx_{\min} and the number of fluid nodes.

Numerical parameter (dx_{\min})	Total number of mesh fluid nodes
0.002 m	20 211 310
0.0015 m	43 132 855
0.0012 m	78 557 344

For GPU the three test cases were executed on one NVIDIA A100 40GB. For CPU cases, LaBS was compiled with GCCcore 8.2.0 and OpenMPI 4.0.5 and 32, 64 and 96 processors were used.

Table 3 contains the MLUPS/proc, Million Lattice Updates per Second per processor, for the solver step, neglecting the pre- and post-processing, focusing only on the performances of the actual calculus of the LBM algorithm. 2000 iterations were performed, and no output files were written during the solver step. The results are visualized in Figure 14.

Table 3: Performance parameters for the simulation of the three test cases on the GPU and on the CPU using different numbers of processors.

dx_{\min}	1 GPU	32 procs		64 procs		96 procs	
	MLUPS/ proc	MLUPS/ proc	GPU/ CPU	MLUPS/ proc	GPU/ CPU	MLUPS/ proc	GPU/ CPU
0.002 m	244.56	1.48	165.24	1.15	212.66	0.76	321.79
0.0015 m	11.31	1.56	7.25	0.97	11.66	0.82	13.79
0.0012 m	7.44	memory overflow	/	1.39	5.35	1.08	6.89

Figure 14: Development of GPU/CPU performance indicator for the three test cases of different numbers of fluid nodes.

The 78 million fluid nodes test case resulted in being too large for running on 32 processors and a memory overflow was detected during the pre-process step. Because the card's memory is very limited, GPU performance collapses in cases of 43 million fluid nodes or more. As a first test, we could test and improve the first version of LaBS running on GPU. For all tests presented here, the GPU version has good performance measured in MLUPS/proc with respect to all CPU tests, at least for these cases and the number of processors used. Increasing the size of the test case and the GPU architecture could lead to more precise study.

5.3. CPU Scalability

Using Karolina clusters, we wanted to test the scalability of LaBS. How many resources do we need to allocate to run a specific test case? If we increase computing resources, how much time will we save? Using the same test case TC1, we decrease the minimum mesh size dx_{\min} , obtaining a test case of 113 219 388 fluid nodes. The same CPU version of LaBS was used, with GCCcore 8.2.0 and OpenMPI 4.0.5. We still neglected the pre-process and post-process step, and we concentrated only on the performances of the actual calculus of the LBM algorithm. 50 000 iterations were performed, and no output files were written during the solver step. We ran several computations on several processors

multiple of $k \cdot 256$, with $k = 1$ to 10. From 256 as reference, on 2 compute nodes, to 2 560 processors, on 20 compute nodes.

Speed up, defined as the ratio of the runtime of the best algorithm for solving a problem to the time taken by the parallel algorithm to solve the same problem on p processors, is calculated as:

$$Speed\ up = \frac{T_{p_ref}}{T_p}$$

Where T_{p_ref} is the Solver time of test case taken as reference, i.e. the one on 256 processors. T_p is the Solver time of the test case on the processor p , with p from 256 to 2560.

The Efficiency, measuring the fraction of time for which a processor is usefully utilized, is calculated as:

$$Efficiency = \frac{(T_{p_ref} * np_ref)}{(T_p * np)}$$

With np_ref being 256, the number of reference processors, np the number of all processors, i.e. from 256 to 2560. Figure 15 displays the results regarding speed up and efficiency over the number of CPUs utilized. The simulation results displayed in Figure 15 are listed in Table 4.

Figure 15: Visualization of speed up and efficiency over the number of processors.

Table 4: Calculated values of ideal and real speed up and efficiency in relation to the number of CPUs utilized and the corresponding solver time.

nproc	256	512	768	1024	1280	1536	1792	2048	2304	2560
Solver time	24982,7	12377,6	9662	6876,1	6132,1	4823	4357,9	4016,4	3599,8	3263
Speed up										
real	1	2,018379	2,585665	3,633266	4,074085	5,179909	5,732738	6,220172	6,940024	7,656359
ideal	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Efficiency										
real	1	1,009189	0,86189	0,908316	0,814817	0,863318	0,818963	0,777521	0,771114	0,765636
ideal	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1

The results indicate a satisfying scalability for the test case in consideration with respect to the number of processors used. Best results up to 1024 processors and no significant collapses for more processors: if we increase the resources, we still have good performances in terms of scalability. A further step could be to consider more complex test cases, adding features or increasing the number of mesh nodes, for example up to 1 billion or more fluid nodes.